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TKA

Economical and environmental evaluation of non-residential demand response in the European transition to zero-carbon energy

by

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Oral PhD examination
25th April 2024

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**Economical and environmental evaluation
of non-residential demand response
in the European transition
to zero-carbon energy**

Motivation and Background

Evaluating the Economic and Environmental Potential of Demand Response (DR)

Challenges

The **impact of DR on carbon emissions** not fully understood.

Complexity in quantifying DR potential in local multi-energy systems (L-MES) hindered DR adoption and investments in clean energy.

Lack of **practical understanding** of non-residential DR potentials.

DR potential must be considered in the design optimization. **Time series aggregation** methods that are used for complexity reduction induce an error, which is not known.

Approach

- Develop data-driven methods and analytical tools and apply them.
- Streamline the quantification process of DR potentials.
- Conduct case studies to gain real-world insights.
- Quantify this error in a real-world case study.

Objectives

1. Develop a method and tool to calculate **dynamic marginal and average grid-mix emission factors** in Europe, assessing the **impact of DR on carbon emissions**.
2. Analyze how price-based DR affects carbon emissions across different **European countries** and **carbon price** levels.
3. Create and test a modular **framework** for evaluating the **DR potential** of L-MES through **optimal design and operations**.
4. Assess their **economic and environmental DR potentials** by **applying the framework** to various non-residential case studies.
5. Evaluate the effectiveness of **time series aggregation** in low-carbon industrial MES models considering DR.

Outline

Presentation

Environmental evaluation of DR

Chapter 3

- Types of carbon emission factors
- Effect of price-based DR on carbon emissions across countries and carbon price levels
- Elmada (open-source tool)

Quantification of local DR potentials

Chapter 4-8

- DRAF (open-source tool)
- Novel flexibility metrics
- Case Studies
 - Production planning
 - Industrial MES
 - Industrial grid fees
 - Hydrogen hubs

Time series aggregation in low-carbon L-MES models

Chapter 9

Contributions and Dissemination

Thesis

Part I: Introduction & Literature Review

Part II: Experimental Studies

Part III: Global Discussion & Conclusions

The background is a dark, almost black, textured surface. It features a faint, glowing map of Europe in the center, with the landmasses appearing as lighter, grainy shapes. Scattered across the entire background are numerous small, bright white and yellowish points, resembling stars or distant galaxies, which create a cosmic or night-sky effect. The overall aesthetic is mysterious and scientific.

Environmental evaluation of DR

Types of carbon emission factors

→ **MEFs** reflect the effect of a load change on carbon emissions

→ **XEFs** reflect the carbon footprint of an electrical load

Environmental evaluation of DR

CEF calculation method

Environmental evaluation of DR

CEF calculation method

8 data sources with more than 10 Million data points

Environmental evaluation of DR

CEF calculation method

Data sources:

Methods: — PP — PWL ... PWLv

... to calculate **merit orders**
for different years (y) and countries (c)
with different methods

Dimensions: time-step year country fuel-type power plant

Quaschnig

EEX

Worldbank

Konstantin

DESTATIS

Carbon emission price (y, f)

Transmission efficiency (c)

Fuel price (y, c, f)

Power plants with marginal price (y, c, p)

Sorting of power plants by marginal prices

Merit order (y, c, p)

Dispatch of conventional power plants (t, y, c)

XEFs (t, y, c)

MEFs (t, y, c)

Environmental evaluation of DR

CEF calculation method

Environmental evaluation of DR

CEF calculation method

If not, the **PWL** method can be used to approximate power plants and efficiencies.

Stilized load shifting simulations

- Select European countries and years with high data quality:
 - **20 European countries**
 - 3 years: 2017-2019.
- Apply PP and PWL method to calculate prices, XEFs and MEFs.
- Simulate: Every day, **1 kWh** is shifted from the **hour with the highest price** to the **hour with the lowest price**.
- Evaluate the average effect on costs and emissions using the MEFs and XEFs.

Results for 20 European countries and the year 2019

based on XEFs

20 European countries

	AT	BE	CZ	DE	DK	ES	FI	FR	GB	GR	HU	IE	IT	LT	NL	PL	PT	RO	RS	SI
Change in Costs (%)	-24	-6	-6	-12	-6	-4	-10	-21	-16	-24	-13	-4	-4	-3	-5	-5	-14	-11	-3	-19
Change in carbon footprint (%)	-53	-45	-21	-37	-38	-10	-10	-92	-57	-3	-13	-30	-3	-53	-1	-7	-20	-20	3	-27
Change in emissions (%)	11	-7	-5	10	-5	25	-4	-64	-3	53	31	3	-4	-3	-5	-1	22	4	-3	-13

based on MEFs

→ Load shifts led to increased carbon emissions for 8 of the 20 countries

Types of carbon emission factors

Merit Order Dilemma of Emissions

Impact of carbon price level

Carbon price Spearman rank correlation
marginal costs vs. emission intensity

Simulated German Merit Order for 2019

	c^{GHG}	r
	0.0 €/t	-0.18
$\bar{c}_{2017}^{\text{GHG}} =$	5.8 €/t	-0.18
$\bar{c}_{2018}^{\text{GHG}} =$	16.0 €/t	-0.16
$\bar{c}_{2019}^{\text{GHG}} =$	24.9 €/t	-0.13
	42.6 €/t	0.00
	65.3 €/t	0.20
	100.0 €/t	0.40
	156.1 €/t	0.60
	235.6 €/t	0.80
	1,269.5 €/t	0.99
	10,000.0 €/t	1.00

Impact of carbon price level

Carbon price Spearman rank correlation
marginal costs vs. emission intensity

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Impact of carbon price level

Spearman correlation between marginal costs and marginal emissions

Impact of carbon price level

	Carbon Price (€/t)										
	0.0	5.8	16.0	24.9	42.6	65.3	100.0	156.1	235.6	1269.5	10000.0
Change in Costs (%)	-28.3	-22.7	-16.0	-12.2	-7.3	-4.1	-6.9	-11.0	-13.7	-19.9	-21.2
Change in carbon footprint (%)	-35.1	-35.1	-34.9	-34.7	-31.8	-37.5	-45.0	-45.1	-45.1	-44.8	-44.7
Change in emissions (%)	10.0	10.0	10.2	6.5	12.7	-7.8	-18.9	-21.0	-20.5	-21.3	-21.4

Elmada (open-source tool)

elmada.

- Methods to calculate MEFs and XEFs were integrated into **Elmada**, a new open-source Python tool.
- Source code available (LGPL License) <https://github.com/DrafProject/elmada>
- Listed in the **Open Sustainable Technology** directory

elmada: Dynamic electricity carbon emission factors and prices for Europe

Status: pypi package v0.1.0 CI with pip no status CI with conda no status codecov 92%

Usage: python 3.9| 3.10| 3.11 License LGPL v3 JOSS 10.21105/joss.03625 downloads 8k

Contribution: imports isort code style black chat on gitter Contributor Covenant 2.0

The open-source Python package **elmada** provides electricity carbon emission factors and wholesale prices for European countries. The target group includes modelers of distributed energy hubs who need electricity market data (short: **elmada**), e.g., to evaluate the environmental effect of demand response. **elmada** is part of the [Draf Project](#) but can be used as a standalone package.

Quantification of local non-residential DR potentials

DRAF (open-source tool)

- **demand response analysis framework (DRAF)** is an open-source Python framework for the economical and environmental evaluation of price-based DR.
- **Aim:** Simplify the quantification of cost and carbon emission savings from DR.
- **Approach:** Multi-objective optimization (MILP)

Demand Response Analysis Framework (DRAF): Architecture

Example local Multi-Energy Systems (L-MES)

Legend: : Storage indicator : Flexible asset **TES**: Thermal energy storage **PV**: Photovoltaic **WT**: Wind turbine **CHP**: Combined heat and power

Production Planning Case Study: Setup

Legend: —: Storage indicator ⚙️: Flexible asset TES: Thermal energy storage PV: Photovoltaic WT: Wind turbine CHP: Combined heat and power

Production Planning Case Study: Results

Quantification of local non-residential DR potentials

Industrial MES Case Study: Setup

Case Study L-MES: Results

➤ Flexibility lead to financial and environmental benefits.

Case Study L-MES: Results

- Decarbonization costs are the cost difference between the optimized decarbonization scenario and the optimized non-decarbonization scenario:

$$C_s^{\text{decarb}} = \text{TAC}_{s_d} - \text{TAC}_s$$

- Even in the moderate carbon removal costs case, having flexibility led to reductions of decarbonization costs by 19%.

Novel Flexibility Metrics

Industrial MES Case Study: Flexibility Metrics

➤ Flexible systems allowed to buy cheaper and greener electricity.

Industrial MES Case Study: Flexibility Metrics

➤ Flexible systems allowed to buy cheaper and greener electricity.

... If carbon removal price is increased from moderate (222 €/t) to very high (10,000 €/t):

Time series aggregation in low-carbon L-MES models

Common TSA Approaches

Typical Periods

Cluster periods into typical periods

Source: Kotzur, 2018

FIGURE 8.2: Exemplary distribution of 12 typical days with 8 segments each.

Common TSA Approaches

Segments

Cluster adjacent hours of a day into segments.

FIGURE 8.2: Exemplary distribution of 12 typical days with 8 segments each.

Common TSA Approaches

Seasonal Storage Formulation

Link typical periods to model long duration storage.

FIGURE 8.1: Scheme of seasonal storage modeling with typical periods.

Literature Review TSA and DR

Article		Used or proposed approach			Considered DR attributes				Analyses		
Year	Reference	Typical periods	Segments	Seasonal storage ¹	Real-time pricing	Dynamic XEFs	Dynamic MEFs	DAC costs	Hyper-parameters ⁴	Back-testing ⁵	Use case(s)
2018	Kotzur et al. [254]	✓							✓		residential & island
2018	Kotzur et al. [255]	✓		✓					✓		residential & island
2018	Gabrielli et al. [256]	✓	✓	✓	✓				✓		urban residential
2019	Baumgärtner et al. [100]	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓				industrial
2019	Baumgärtner et al. [257]	✓	✓		✓						industrial
2019	Gabrielli et al. [258]	✓		✓	✓ ²				✓	✓	urban residential
2019	Kannengießer et al. [259]	✓		✓					✓		residential urban & island
2019	Tejada-Arango et al. [260]	✓		✓					✓		national
2020	Pinel [261]	✓		✓	✓	✓			✓		residential
2021	Hering et al. [262]	✓				✓					district heating
2021	Hoettecke et al. [263]	✓			✓				✓		industrial
2021	Hoffmann et al. [264]	✓	✓	✓					✓		residential & national
2021	Wirtz et al. [265]	✓		✓	✓						research campus
2021	Yokoyama et al. [266]	✓							✓		district heating & cooling
2022	Blanke et al. [267]	✓		✓					✓		industrial
2022	Göke and Kendzioriski [268]	✓		✓					✓		national
2022	Hoettecke et al. [269]	✓			✓	✓		✓ ³			industrial
2022	Hoffmann et al. [270]	✓	✓						✓		international & local
2022	Kuepper et al. [271]	✓							✓	✓	national
2023	Ma et al. [272]	✓		✓	✓				✓		local
2023	Thiran et al. [273]	✓		✓					✓		multi-regional
2023	Our study	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	industrial

Methodology: Backtest-based error calculation

- **original model:** Full-year based design and operation
- **TSA Model:** TSA-based design and operation
- **Backtest (BT) model:** TSA-based design but full-year-based operation

TSA Case Study

→ Industrial case study without electric vehicles

Results: Assumed vs. Total TSA-induced error

Generally

- Total TSA-induced error increases with increasing aggregation intensity

Non-decarbonization case:

- Total error below 5% even for 99.9% time series reduction

Decarbonization case:

- High emission error adds to cost error (depending on carbon removal price)

Results: A Priori vs. a Posteriori error

- A priori error deviates significantly from a posteriori error
- A posteriori error can highly vary depending on model constraints

Contribution and Dissemination

Contributions

Primary contributions

- ✓ **elmada**, an open-source tool for calculating electricity carbon emission factors.
- ✓ **Analysis** of how price-based **DR affects carbon emissions** across different **European countries** and **carbon price** levels.
- ✓ Development and demonstration of **DRAF**, an open-source Python framework for **evaluating the DR potential** of local MESs through **optimal design and operation**.
- ✓ Evaluation of non-residential DR potentials on various **real-world case studies**.
- ✓ Evaluate the effectiveness of **time series aggregation** in low-carbon industrial MES models considering DR.

Contributions

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Secondary contributions

- ✓ **Data** for European historic carbon emission factors
- ✓ **Model formulations** of distributed energy resources
- ✓ **Flexibility metrics**
- ✓ Definition and demonstration of **TSA errors metrics** from an investor's perspective.

Dissemination

Open-source Software

- **4** direct email requests
- Was used by multiple PhD students.
- **5** unique GitHub visitors in the last 2 weeks
- **7750** downloads via PyPI link in **2** years.
(**74** downloads per week)

Dissemination

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(**74** downloads per week)

- Usage and further development by a known PhD student
- **14** unique GitHub visitors in the last 2 weeks

First-authored Journal Paper

- | | | |
|------------------|--|----|
| 1. | M. Fleschutz, M. Bohlayer, M. Braun, G. Henze, M. D. Murphy (2021). Title: "The effect of price-based demand response on carbon emissions in European electricity markets: The importance of adequate carbon prices". Journal: Applied Energy, Issue: 295 (May).
https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2021.117040 | 85 |
| 2. | M. Fleschutz, M. D. Murphy (2021). Title: "elmada: Dynamic electricity carbon emission factors and prices for Europe". Journal: Journal of Open Source Software, Volume: 6, Issue: 66. https://doi.org/10.21105/joss.03625 | 12 |
| 3. | M. Fleschutz, M. Bohlayer, M. Braun, M. D. Murphy (2022). Title: "Demand Response Analysis Framework (DRAF): An Open-Source Multi-Objective Decision Support Tool for Decarbonizing Local Multi-Energy Systems". Journal: Sustainability, Volume: 14, Issue: 13. https://doi.org/10.3390/su14138025 | 17 |
| 4. | M. Fleschutz, M. Bohlayer, M. Braun, M. D. Murphy (2023). Title: "From prosumer to flexumer: Case study on the value of flexibility in decarbonizing the multi-energy system of a manufacturing company". Journal: Applied Energy, Issue: 347 (October). https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2023.121430 | 8 |
| 5. | M. Fleschutz, M. Bohlayer, M. Braun, M. D. Murphy (2024, under Review at Energy). Title: "The hidden cost of using time series aggregation for modeling low-carbon industrial energy systems: An investors' perspective". https://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4796211 (Preprint) | - |
| Citations | | |
| Σ: 122 | | |

First-authored Conference Paper

1. **M. Fleschutz**, M. Bohlayer, A. Bürger, M. Braun (2017). Title: "Electricity Cost Reduction Potential of Industrial Processes using Real Time Pricing in a Production Planning Problem". Event: Collaborative European Research Conference (CERC). [Link to proceedings](#) 1
2. **M. Fleschutz**, A. Leippi, M. Bohlayer, M. Braun, M. D. Murphy (2022). Title: "Industrial grid fees vs. demand response: A case study of a multi-use battery in a German chemical plant". Event: Conference on the European Energy Market 2022. <https://doi.org/10.1109/EEM54602.2022.9921156> 1
3. **M. Fleschutz**, D. Bull, M. Braun, M. D. Murphy (2023). Title: "Impact of Landing Interruptions on the Optimal Design and Operation of Green Hydrogen Hubs". Event: IEEE ISGT Europe 2023. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ISGTEUROPE56780.2023.10408039>

Citations

Σ : 2

Co-authored Journal Paper

1. M. Bohlayer, **M. Fleschutz**, M. Braun, G. Zöttl (2020). Title: "Energy-intense production-inventory planning with participation in sequential energy markets". Journal: Applied Energy, Issue: 258 (June 2019). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2019.113954> 16
2. M. Bohlayer, A. Bürger, **M. Fleschutz**, M. Braun, G. Zöttl (2021). Title: "Multi-period investment pathways - Modeling approaches to design distributed energy systems under uncertainty". Journal: Applied Energy, Issue: 285 (December 2020). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2020.116368> 23
3. A. Leippi, **M. Fleschutz**, M. D. Murphy (2022). Title: "A Review of EV Battery Utilization in Demand Response Considering Battery Degradation in Non-Residential Vehicle-to-Grid Scenarios". Journal: Energies, Volume: 15, Issue: 9. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en15093227> 20

Citations
 Σ : 59

Co-authored Conference Paper

1. M. Bohlayer, **M. Fleschutz**, A. Bürger, M. Braun (2017). Title: „Multi-objective optimization of a waste heat driven heating supply system using Mixed-Integer-Programming“. Event: Collaborative European Research Conference (CERC). [Link to proceedings](#)
2. M. Bohlayer, **M. Fleschutz**, M. Braun, G. Zöttl (2018). Title: „Demand side management and the participation in consecutive energy markets-a multistage stochastic optimization approach“. Event: Conference on the European Energy Market 2018 9
3. D. Bull, A. Bürger, M. Bohlayer, **M. Fleschutz**, M. Braun (2021). Title: „Enabling decentralized demand side management in industrial energy supply systems“. Event: INFORMATIK 2020. https://doi.org/10.18420/inf2020_100
4. A. Leippi, **M. Fleschutz**, K. Davis, MD. Murphy (2022). Title: „Utilization of electric vehicle fleets in industrial demand response considering vehicle-to-grid benefits and battery degradation“. Event: „Event: Conference on the European Energy Market 2022“. <https://doi.org/10.1109/EEM54602.2022.9921000> 1

Citations
 Σ : 10

Dissemination

Scientific Publications

8 first-authored papers

5 Journal | 3 Conference

7 Co-authored papers

3 Journal | 4 Conference

→ **124 citations**

→ **69 citations**

→ **193 total citations (H-index: 8)**

→ Mentioned on German [Flexumer Wikipedia article](#):

Wirtschaftliche Potenziale [Bearbeiten | Quelltext bearbeiten]
 Bislang haben sich wenige Studien mit den wirtschaftlichen Potenzialen von Flexufern beschäftigt. Erste Forschungsergebnisse (Fleschutz et al, 2023^[10]) im Bereich des produzierenden Gewerbes weisen darauf hin, dass erhebliche wirtschaftliche Vorteile erzielt werden können, wenn Flexibilitätspotenziale ausgeschöpft werden. Durch

The effect of price-based demand response in electricity markets: The importance of...
 Markus Fleschutz^{a,b}, Markus Bohlayer^{a,c}, Marco Braun^a, Michael D. Murphy^{b,*}

ARTICLE INFO
 Keywords: Price-based demand response, Time-dependent carbon emission factor

Article
Demand Response and An Open-Source Multi-Energy System for Decarbonizing Low-Carbon Regions
 Markus Fleschutz^{1,2}, Markus Bohlayer^{1,2}

ABSTRACT
 Price-based demand response potential. High marginal emission factors...

Dynamic electricity prices for Europe
 Markus Fleschutz¹

ABSTRACT
 multi-energy system...

DOI: 10.21105/joss.03625

Applied Energy 347 (2023) 121430
 Contents lists available at ScienceDirect
Applied Energy
 journal homepage: www.elsevier.com/locate/apenergy

From prosumer to flexumer: Case study on the value of flexibility in decarbonizing the multi-energy system of a manufacturing company
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Thank you!

NEXT:
Q & A